

Application of two types of bio-fertilizer to improve irrigated rice growth and yield

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ABSTRACT

Fertilizer plays an essential role in supporting the Indonesia Food Resilience Program. Nowadays, biological fertilizer has increasingly used to optimize the uptake of nutrients in the soil by plants. The purpose of this research was to obtain the most appropriate composition of biological fertilizer in increasing rice productivity of irrigated land. The experiment was conducted in the irrigation area of Punimbe sub-viullages (location 1) and Bageq Nunggal sub-village (location 2) of Ubung Village, Jonggat District, Central Lombok Regency of West Nusa Tenggara at the dry season I (April-June 2017). Different biofertilizers were applied in each location, namely Bio-phosphate for location 1 and Ecofert for location 2, both of which play an N and solvent P. Inorganic fertilizer of urea fertilizer and NPK Phonska were applied based on the recommendation of integrated plant calendar (KATAM) for the District of Jonggat which was 200 kg/ha for each Urea and NPK Phonska (15:15:15). The experiment was arranged with a randomized block design for five treatments and repeated five times. The five treatments were: 100% treatment recommended dose of Bio-Phosphate (BP 4) and ecofert (Eco 4) equivalent to 50 kg/ha; 75% recommended dose or equivalent to 37,5 kg/ha (BP 3 and Eco 3); 50% recommended dose or equivalent to 25 kg/ha (BP 2 and Eco 2); 25% recommended dose or equivalent to 12,5kg/ha (BP 1 and Eco 1); and without the use of biological fertilizers as a control (BP 0 and Eco 0). The result showed that there were significant differences between rice crops given ecofert and control at the vegetative stage, but at generative parameters has showed no significant difference effect except on the grain weight. The highest yield was obtained from the treatment of P2, which was giving 75% Ecofert dosage.

Keywords: *organic fertilizer, production, rice, phosphate, Ecofert*

INTRODUCTION

Fertilization efficiency is still an obstacle in efforts to increase the productivity of rice, especially the nature of each nutrient contained in fertilizer which is quite diverse. Nitrogen nutrients are one of the elements that are needed by plants, especially rice from the vegetative to generative phases, as well as affecting soil conditions, especially the level of acidity (Rohmah et al., 2016). However, its highly hygroscopic nature requires special treatment both in

determining the quantity and method of application. In contrast to Nitrogen, Phosphorus nutrients are even more difficult to be available for plants because of its nature to be absorbed in the soil and greatly affect the availability of other elements such as C-organic (Citraresmini and Bachtiar, 2016). If fertilization handling can be done properly, optimal conditions will be obtained in the soil for plant growth while increasing the productivity of rice plants.

N and P nutrients play an important role in supporting plant growth and yield (Fahmi et al., 2010). These two elements are mostly obtained from inorganic fertilizers, but their increasing and excessive use has a negative impact on the environment and ultimately economically decreases farmers' income. The addition of inorganic fertilizer does not necessarily increase the availability of nutrients in the soil for plants, even on rice fields that are intensively processed and using excess chemical fertilizers cause soil organic matter content to decrease, and reduce the level of biological and physical fertility of the soil (Romli, 2012; Hasna et al., 2018).

The above description cause the productivity of crops cultivated, especially rice, to decline, thus impacting on the low profits gained in the farming. Provision of organic materials in the form of organic fertilizer and biological fertilizers needs to be done to overcome these things. Various research results indicate the application of organic fertilizers combined with anorganic fertilizer can improve crop yields (Dewanto et al., 2013; Purnomo, 2013; Simanjuntak et al., 2013; Perwita et al., 2017), as well improve farm efficiency (syafuruddin, 2011).

Research on the effectiveness of biological agents of phosphate solvents and N-fastening agents has been carried out in various commodities including rice fields (Setiawati, 2014), upland rice (Alavan et al., 2015), corn (Arifin et al., 2010), soybeans, shallots (Anisyah et al., 2014; Rosita et al., 2016), lettuce (hayati, 2010), tomatoes (Astuti, Widodo and Budisantosa, 2013), to annual crops (Mashud et al., 2013). The aim of this study was to obtain the appropriate dose of N and P-phosphate and Ecofert P-fertilizer application to increase the rate of growth and production of rice plants on irrigated land.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted at two locations in the fields owned by farmers, the first is at Punimbe sub-village (-08,64419 S and 116.18856 E) and the second at Bageq Nunggal sub-village (-8,67002 S and 116.19537 E). Both of these locations are at Ubung Village, Jonggat Subdistrict, Central Lombok Regency NTB. The study was carried out in the second planting season (MK I) of May to July 2017. The average monthly rainfall at the time of the study was 5 mm; 92 mm and 93 mm for May, June and July, respectively. While the number of rainy

days is 5, 8 and 8 days rainy. The average temperature at the time of the study was 26.4 0C; 25.7 0C and 25.1 0C.

Different biofertilizers are applied in each location, namely Bio-phosphate for location 1 and Ecofert for location 2, both of which play an N and solvent P. Both of these fertilizers are applied directly into the soil which serves to improve soil fertility while increasing agricultural production (Nursanti, 2017). Sastro et al., (2005) also reported that the use of bio-phosphate fertilizer was able to increase nutrient uptake of P far than KH₂PO₄ fertilizer, rock phosphate fertilizer and without P fertilizer on ultisols soil at 214.1%, 382.3% and 668.3% respectively.

Table 1. The content of nutrients and microorganisms in N-fixing biofertilizers and solvents of Bio-phosphate and Ecofert P.

Parameters	Unit	Biofertilizer 1 (Bio Fosfat)	Biofertilizer 2 (Ecofert)
P ₂ O ₅	%	17-20	-
CaO	%	33	-
pH		7,7	-
Micro element		S, MgO, Zn, Cu, Mn, B, Mo.	-
The content of microorganism		Aspergillus, Trichoderma, Azotobacter and Pseudomonas	N-fixing bacteria and P. solvents

The experiment was designed using a randomized block design (RBD) method consisting of seven combinations of urea dose treatment with the addition of organic liquid fertilizer (biourin) with five replications where the natural plots belonged to farmers as replications. The seven treatments are the use of 200 kg urea dose / ha + 0% Biourin (P1); Urea 200 kg / ha + 10% Biourin (P2); Urea 200 kg / ha + Biourin 20% (P3); Urea 150 kg / ha + Biourin 10% (P4); Urea 150 kg / ha + Biourin 20% (P5); Urea 100 kg / ha + Biourin 10% (P6); and finally the use of urea dose as much as 100 kg / ha + Biourin 20% (P7). The use of biourin doses is only two levels, namely 10% and 20% based on the research of Tantawizal and Nazam (2017) in Setanggor Village, Central Lombok Regency in the second planting season (ICM) which shows that the highest rice growth and production is obtained from 10-15%, so in this study it is expected that an inorganic fertilizing formula (urea) will be obtained with an appropriate and optimum POC biourin. The use of the highest dose of urea in the treatment (200 kg / ha) was based on the recommendation of the integrated planting calendar (KATAM) for the Jonggat Subdistrict in the second planting season (MK) for rice crops that were planted without using additional organic fertilizer either straw or compost. Likewise with Phonska NPK fertilizer, using doses that are in

accordance with KATAM recommendations and applied the same for all treatments that is 200 kg / ha, and applied twice that is 60-75% when the plant is 10 days after moving.

The application of Urea and Biourin fertilizer given to each experimental plot was carried out as recommended in integrated crop management, where urea fertilizer was given three stages and Biourin was applied 5 times during intermittent planting season one week starting from the age of 11 days after moving. The age of the plant when it was moved from the location of the research location nursery was 17 days.

Table 2. The analysis result at study site (Punimbe hamblet, Ubung village, Jonggat district,, Central Lombok Regency, NTB)

Parameter	unit	testing result	Hara Status	method
pH-H ₂ O	-	7.16	neutral	pH-meter
N-NH ₄	ppm	14.45	medium	Kjeldahl
N-NO ₃	ppm	16.75	medium	Devarda Alloy
N-Total	%	0.17	low	Kjeldahl
C-Organic	%	0.43	very low	Kurmish
sand	%	57		Hydrometer
dudt	%	23		Hydrometer
clayey	%	20		Hydrometer
class Tekstur				sandy loam
P ₂ O ₅ -Bray	ppm	7.86	medium	Bray
K-dd	cmol/kg	0.44	medium	AAS
Na-dd	cmol/kg	0.21	low	AAS
Ca-dd	cmol/kg	6.29	medium	AAS
Mg-dd	cmol/kg	0.74	low	AAS
KTK	cmol/kg	12.58	low	Percolations

Note: the analysis result of soil and fertilizer laboratory of BPTP Balitbangta NTB, 2016 .

Globally the soil chemical conditions at the study site for N and P macro nutrients are relatively low, while K is classified as medium. Micro nutrients are categorized as low to moderate in locations 1 and 2. Soil texture in both locations is the same as sandy clay and neutral pH.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research locations 1 and 2 have the same landform in agro-ecosystem. The type of soil at the study site is included in the sub-order typic epiaquerts with an aquic moisture regime and inhibited drainage type. Forming land at the study site is a volcanic foot fault, made from parent breccia and lava, with flat relief so that it is grouped into zone IV in the agro-ecological zone classification of agricultural land and recommended for food crop wetland subsystems as existing land use.

The effect of Bio Phosphate on Vegetative stage

Vegetatif phase response of rice plants which were given additional bio-phosphate biofertilizers with several dosage variations showed significant differences for both plant height parameters at 30 and 60 day after planting (DAP) and harvest time. While the parameters of the number of tillers were found to be significant differences in the 30 DAP phase and at harvest, when 60 DAP was not significantly different (table 3.)

Table 3. The vegetative phase response of rice plants to the treatment of several Bio-phosphate doses at the study site

Treat	Plant Height at 30 DAP (cm)	Plant Height at 60 DAP (cm)	Plant Height at Harvest (cm)	Tiller number perclump at 30 DAP	Tiller number perclump at 60 DAP	Tiller number perclump at Harvest	Tiller number perclump Productive
BP 0	51.6ab	78.4b	93.4b	14b	16.4	15.2b	14.6
BP 1	49.8b	79b	99.2a	14.2b	17.4	17.8ab	17
BP 2	52ab	78b	97.8ab	14b	18	16.2ab	15.4
BP 3	51.4ab	81ab	99.2a	16ab	20.4	20a	17
BP 4	54.8a	83.4a	97.2ab	17.2a	17.4	18.6ab	17.2
LSD	4.92	4.125	4.623	2.503	4.002	3.901	3.614
notation	*	*	*	*	ns	*	ns

note: BP (Bio-phosphate); ns (not significantly different); the number followed by the same letter in the same column show no significant difference based on the 5% DMRT advance test.

The height of rice plants that are not applied by Bio phosphate fertilizer tends to be the lowest. and is significantly different from the treatment of BP 1 and BP 3 at the last observation/at harvest. This indicates that the application of bio-phosphate fertilizer with doses of 25% and 75% of recommendations can provide optimal growth for rice plants in paddy fields. The difference in plant height for each treatment can be seen in Figure 1. While variations in the number of tillers at 30 DAP, 60 DAP, the total number of tillers and the number of productive tillers for each treatment can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The difference in plant height for each bio phosphate treatment

Slightly different from plant height parameters, the number of tillers was significantly different between control rice plants and rice plants which were given bio-phosphate biofertilizer treatment only in the phase 30 days after planting and at harvest. The number of tillers during observation was 60 days after planting and the number of productive tillers did not differ significantly in each treatment or control. This is presumably because it is related to the function of phosphorus in stimulating root growth, especially at the beginning of growth, accelerating flowering, cooking seeds and fruit. So that P nutrients absorbed by P solvent microbes contained in the soil are maximally utilized by plants.

Figure 2. The difference in Tiller number per clump for each bio phosphate treatment at 30 DAP, 60 DAP, the total number of tillers and the number of productive tillers number per clump

Ecofert biofertilizer on Vegetative Stage of Rice

Ecofert biofertilizer application on rice plants at the site of assessment of rice observed vegetative and generative parameters. Plant height development when phase 30 days after planting (DAP), 60 DAP, until the time of harvest looks quite diverse in each treatment (figure 3). In phase 30 the DAP shows that the best plant height is shown in rice plants with ecofert application dose 100% recommendation, then followed by a 75% dose recommendation and continues to decrease to 0% dose or only use inorganic fertilizer. Whereas in the next observation that is 60 DAP shows that plant growth in the application of 75% dose recommendations exceeds the 100% dose recommendation.

Figure 3. The difference in plant height for each treatment

In observing the height of the crop at harvest shows that on rice plants without ecofert application or 0% recommendations give the highest number, so it can be said that there is an ineffectiveness of plant physiological growth which should in this phase the growth process no longer occur, but concentrated on filling pods and seed maturation period. While for the number of tillers parameters it is seen that the highest number of tillers is at 30 days, 60 days after planting and when harvest is from the Eco 2 process or 50% Ecofert recommendation. But the number of tillers is very guaranteed to be obtained from the surface of Eco 0 and Eco 1 (figure 4). This was not positively correlated with the lowest fill grain parameter found at Eco Eco 0 and followed by Eco 2, while the fill grain was the highest of Eco 4, Eco 3 and Eco 1.

Figure 4. The difference in Tiller number per clump and filled grain for each treatment

Figure 4 shows the diversity of parameters of the number of tillers at the age of 30 days after planting, 60 days after planting and at harvest, as well as the parameters of the number of productive tillers, filled grain and empty grain. In general, each ecofert treatment has a positive effect where the addition of ecofert doses has an impact on increasing the quantity and quality of the number of tillers and the number of grain. The results of the diversity analysis showed that the parameters of the number of tillers and grains were not significantly different, but the parameters of the content of the seedlings were significantly different from the treatment of Eco 4 with Eco 0 but not significantly different from Eco 1, Eco 2 and Eco 3.

Table 4. The vegetative phase response of rice plants to the treatment of several ecofert doses at the study site

treat	Plant Height at 30 DAP (cm)	Plant Height at 60 DAP (cm)	Plant Height at Harvest (cm)	Tiller number per clump at 30 DAP	Tiller number per clump at 60 DAP	Tiller number per clump at Harvest	Tiller number per clump Productive
Eco 0	57.4a	79ab	89.6	16	13.6	15.6	14.8
Eco 1	57a	81.4a	89.4	17.2	13.4	15.2	15.2
Eco 2	53.8ab	76ab	90.6	19.2	17	18.2	17
Eco 3	55.2a	74b	91.2	16.4	12.6	19	18
Eco 4	48.8b	75ab	92.8	15	14.6	19	18.4
LSD	5.85	7.04	4.90	4.54	4.93	5.11	5.11

note: Eco (biofertilizer Ecofert); ns (not significantly different); figures followed by the same letter in the same column show no significant difference based on the 5% Least Significant Difference for advanced analysis.

The of Bio Phospate on Generative Stage of Rice

The highest total grain yield was obtained from the treatment of BP 1 and followed by BP 2. The results of the measurement of the parameter diversity in length and the total amount for all treatments were not different in all treatments. However, the amount of grain looks different between BP 4 and BP 0, BP 1, BP 2 and BP 3. While the parameters for the number of unhulled grains appear to be different between BP 4 and BP 1 but not different from BP 0, BP 2 and BP 3, between BP 0, BP 1, BP 2 and BP 3 are not significantly different. This indicates that the amount of bio-phosphate biofertilizer dose is positive for the quality of grain.

Table 5. Generatif phase response of rice plants to the treatment of several bio phosphate doses at the study site

Treatment	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grain	Unfield grain	Total grain
BP 0	24.13	109b	23ab	133
BP 1	24.27	118ab	28a	146
BP 2	23.2	121ab	20ab	141
BP 3	23.13	112b	18ab	130
BP 4	23.93	125a	13b	138
LSD	1.19	15.3	12.4	18.2
notation	ns	*	*	ns

note: ns (not significantly different); figures followed by the same letter in the same column show no significant difference based on the 5% DMRT advance test.

Effect of Ecofert on Generative Stage of Rice

The generative parameters show that the highest production was obtained from 75% of the recommendations for both dry harvest grain (GKP) and milled dry grain (GKG) which were 6.2 t/ha and 4.98 t/ha, respectively. The weight of the grain at the second highest harvest was obtained from the ecofert application 100% recommendation, however, the weight of the grain after being converted to MPD was lower than the 25% dose.

Overall the results obtained from rice plants that are not given additional biofertilizers or purely using inorganic fertilizers give the lowest values both in GKP and on MPD. This shows that the addition of N-fixing microbes and P solvents on the soil is able to optimize the productivity of paddy field rice seeds in MK I in Ubung Village, Jonggat District, Central Lombok Regency. The optimal dosage obtained from the results of this study can be

applied to different lands but has the same typology of land as the location description.

Considering that N and P nutrients are essentially essential macro nutrients needed by plants, especially rice, the addition of biological fertilizers containing N-fixing microbes and P solvents certainly impacts on the availability of these two nutrients for plants, in addition to affecting physical properties. and the soil biology. Talking about the optimal dose of land typology at the study site it can be said that the addition of N-fixing microbes and P solvents has been seen at a dose of 50-75% in both the growth phase and the generative phase.

Figure 5. The difference production and water content for each treatment

CONCLUSIONS

The use of both N-fixing biofertilizers and P solvents from Bio phosphate and ecofert influence the vegetative and generative phases of irrigated rice plants in the second planting season in Ubung Village, Jonggat District, Central Lombok Regency. The lowest growth and yield obtained from plants was not given biofertilizers. In the bio-phosphate treatment the best growth and yield was obtained at 100% dose recommendation of 50 kg/ha. In ecofert treatment the highest yield was obtained at 75% of its recommendation although this was not significant difference with 50% and 100% of its recommendation. ∴ Thus, it was recommended that biofertilizer application for lowland rice plants on irrigated land with clay soil texture is 100% for bio fosfat and 50-75% for ecofert. The use of N-fixing microbes and P solvents in different locations with different types of land typologies may needs to be studied more deeply in order to obtain more accurate recommendation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research was funded by the DIPA AIAT NTB, Ministry of Agriculture. We would like to express our fully thank to Prof. Kazuyuki Inubushi (Chiba University, Japan), Dr. Reiner Wassmann (IRRI, Philippines), and Dr. Kazuyuki Yagi (NARO, Japan) for their valuable comments on the earlier version of this manuscript.

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